

THERMAL RESISTANT BLENDS OF BISMALIMIDE WITH POLYPHENYLENE OXIDE

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SUMMARY: The blends of Bismaleimide (BMI) and Polyphenylene oxide (PPO) were prepared with the aims of toughening BMI and improving PPO's thermal and chemical resistance. Good miscibility was exhibited in the BMI/PPO blends prepared by a solution method. A dispersion of the BMI phase in the blends was found with an increase in the PPO content in an optical microscopic study. In the form of filler particles, PPO affected the curing and melting behaviours of BMI. An increase in the curing temperature and a decrease in the reaction heat were observed in DSC studies, while the melting process tended to be more independent of the presence of PPO. The improvement in the PPO's thermostability was confirmed in the blends through TGA and TMA analyses, and the semi-IPN structure was verified through TGA experiments.

KEYWORDS: bismaleimide (BMI), polyphenylene oxide (PPO), blends, semi-IPN, thermal resistant material

INTRODUCTION

In less than twenty years advanced composites have been established as efficient high-performance structural materials. Among them, the polyimide matrix composites are widely used as heat-resistant polymeric materials in a variety of civil and military applications including aircraft structures, aeropropulsion, missiles and space vehicles. Although polyimides are excellent materials in thermal-oxidative stability, most of them have the drawback of poor processability and their practical applications are thus greatly restricted. However, Bismaleimide (BMI) offers a comprehensively good performance in both thermostability and processability. Its advantages over common epoxy in better thermal-oxidative stability are attributed to its high crosslink density and the aromatic and heterocyclic structures in the network. In addition to its thermal-oxidative stability, a low moisture absorption can be achieved because the imide functionality has lower capacity for hydrogen bonding than -OH or -NH₂ containing polymers. Most significantly, BMI resins can be fabricated using epoxy-like conditions and the addition polymerization mechanism gives void-free structures. Hot-melt and solution methods are commonly applied to impregnate fibres in the preparation of BMI composites. Compression moulding, autoclave moulding, filament winding and even resin transfer moulding (RTM) are all practical methods in making BMI composites [1].

Nevertheless, the inherent brittleness in BMI materials has been the major disadvantage which limits their application. They are usually high modulus materials with very low elongation at break. Other problems include the susceptibility to microcracking and the tendency of impact damage in composite laminates. Therefore, modification of BMI to improve its brittleness without a drastic sacrifice in high-temperature performance has aroused much interest in the field of material research and development. A number of methods have been explored in this aspect. One of the popular methods is through the copolymerization with reactive modifiers, such as diamine and diallyl compounds. Other chemicals including epoxy, divinyl benzene and vinyl ester resins have also been tried. Various complicated reactions are yet involved in the modification, and a lot of work still needs to be done before the chemistry and kinetics are clearly known and the microstructure and final properties of the material understood. Another convenient method in modifying BMI is blending with engineering thermoplastics. Through blending with appropriate high-performance thermoplastics, desirable thermal-mechanical properties may be imparted to the BMI to produce blends with promising behaviours. It has been concluded that the backbone chemistry, molecular weight, toughness of the thermoplastics, as well as the adhesion between the phases, influence the toughness properties of the corresponding BMI blend system [2,3]. Some authors [4-8] have also studied blends of modified BMI with thermoplastics including polysulfone, polyether sulfone, polyether imide, poly(arylene ether ketone), and encouraging results have been revealed.

As one of the commonly used engineering thermoplastics, polyphenylene oxide (PPO) has superior mechanical properties and excellent processability. Although PPO is quite adequate for certain practical high temperature applications, its thermo-oxidative stability is much worse than most polyimides. Through blending with BMI to form a semi-IPN structure, its high temperature performance is expected to be improved. Moreover, chemical resistance is also expected to be improved as a result of the semi-IPN structure.

In this paper, PPO was used as the thermoplastic modifier in the blending modification of BMI. The miscibility of the BMI with the PPO was studied. DSC, TMA and TGA were utilised in the investigation of the thermal and mechanical behaviours of the blends.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals

Most chemicals were purchased from Aldrich Chemical Company (USA): 1,1'-(Methylene-di-4,1-phenylene)-bismaleimide (BMI), 95%; Poly(2,6-dimethyl-1,4-phenylene oxide); Diethylene chloromethane; trichloromethane.

Material preparation and characterization

A mixed solvent of dichloromethane and trichloromethane was used in the solution blending of PPO with BMI. After the solvent was stripped off, the samples were dried under vacuum. In order to study the morphology before curing, the blend solutions were degassed in an ultrasonic bath and applied to glass plates to obtain thin samples when dried under vacuum. The films were studied using episcopic light in a Nikon Microphot FXA microscope. A Perkin-Elmer DSC 7 was used to investigate the melting and curing behaviours of the BMI, PPO and their blends. Compression moulding was applied for the curing process. The

thermogravimetric and thermomechanical performances of the blends were evaluated using a Perkin-Elmer TGA 7 and TMA systems.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Miscibility of the blends

Both cured and uncured samples of the blends with different compositions were observed under an optical microscope. The miscibility of the BMI and PPO in the blends prepared by the solution method is fairly good and the two phases are evenly distributed. The microscope photos in Fig. 1 show the change in morphology in relation to the PPO content. It can be seen from the pictures that the size of the BMI particles decreases with an increase in the PPO content. When the PPO content exceeds 50%, a continuous phase of PPO is formed, with the BMI dispersed inside it in the form of filler particles. This is more obviously shown in the picture for the sample with 45% PPO under higher magnification in which BMI spreads into very fine particles distributed in the PPO continuous phase. Upon curing, the BMI particles disappear as they first melt and then undergo the crosslinking reaction to form the semi-IPN structure where the PPO phase is confined in the BMI network.

DSC melting and curing behaviours

As a crystalline monomer with reactive polyfunctional maleimide groups, BMI melts upon heating and undergoes the curing reaction under high temperatures, even in the absence of an initiator. A three-dimensional network structure is formed as a result of crosslinking during curing. In the DSC thermogram (Fig. 2), the endothermic peak around 156 °C represents the melting of BMI, while the broad exothermic peak over the temperature range of 170 ~ 270 °C indicates the release of reaction heat during the curing process. PPO is one of the high-performance engineering plastics with stable thermal-properties over a wide temperature range: only a small endothermal peak appears around 250°C, inferring its melting at this temperature. PPO itself does not participate in the crosslinking reaction during the curing process, but it acts as a filler and affects BMI's melting and curing behaviours.

Fig. 1: Photo micrographs of BMI and BMI/PPO blends
a) BMI (x100) before curing, b) 30%PPO (x100) before curing, c) 70%PPO (x100) before curing,
d) BMI (x100) after curing, e) 30%PPO (x100) after curing, f) 70%PPO (x100) after curing,
g) 45%PPO (x400) before curing

Fig. 2: DSC thermograms for BMI & PPO
($20^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, N_2)

Fig. 3: DSC thermograms for BMI/PPO
($20^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, N_2)

The DSC melting and curing behaviours for the blends show different dependence on the composition. The thermograms for BMI and its blends with PPO of contents up to 50% are shown in Fig. 3. It can be seen that as the PPO content increases the curing peak shifts to higher temperature and is broadened, while the melting peak remains quite steady at its position. It is known that parameters obtained from DSC are strongly dependent upon the scanning rate used in dynamic DSC testing. In order to find the zero-scanning DSC parameters, experiments at a series of scanning rates, 2.5, 5, 10, $20^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, were performed on samples of various compositions and the data were processed by extrapolation against the scanning rate. The extrapolated curing temperature tends to increase and the reaction heat tends to decrease, even after considering the weight change of BMI in the blends of different compositions (Table 1 and Fig. 4). It is concluded that although the PPO phase in the blends brings toughness to the material through lowering the crosslinking density of the network, it increases the steric hindrance at the reactive maleimido groups in curing, and therefore shows a tendency to retard the BMI's curing reaction. On the other hand, the melting of BMI seems more independent of the composition changes in the blends. The extrapolated melting temperature fluctuates only within a narrow range and the melting enthalpy is fairly constant after correction for blend composition (broken line in Fig. 5). Part of the reason for this may be that melting is more likely a local behaviour and not prone to the influence of the environment in which BMI monomers are situated.

Table 1 DSC parameters for BMI and its blends at zero-scanning rate

PPO% (wt.)	Melting			Curing		
	T _p (°C)	ΔH (J/g)	ΔH (J/g)*	T _p (°C)	ΔH (J/g) ⁺	ΔH (J/g)*
0	155.5	61.6	61.6	182.1	-107.1	-107.1
10	157.3	56.7	63.0	203.2	-71.8	-79.7
20	157.1	51.2	64.0	208.8	-50.5	-63.1
30	158.4	47.0	67.1	208.0	-60.0	-85.7
40	157.8	43.0	71.7	208.9	-52.0	-86.7
50	158.0	34.5	69.0	205.4	-39.9	-79.8

+ Negative values of enthalpy indicate an exothermic process

* After correction for composition of the blend

Fig. 4 Extrapolated DSC parameters in curing of BMI with different PPO contents

Fig. 5 Extrapolated DSC parameters in melting of BMI with different PPO contents

Kinetic study

DSC is a quick and convenient method with which to study the reaction kinetics. Compared with the Borchardt-Daniels method, which is generally used by the commercial software packaged with many DSC systems, the Kissinger method is more suitable for modelling multiple consecutive reactions [9]. It deals with the position of the peak maximum obtained under various DSC scanning rates, and it is based on the following equation:

$$\ln(\phi / T_p^2) = -E / RT_p + \ln(AR / E)$$

where ϕ is the scanning rate (K/min), T_p is the peak temperature in Kelvin, E and A are the apparent activation energy (kJ/mol) and the frequency factor respectively. A plot of $\ln(\phi / T_p^2)$ against $1/T_p$ will provide the solution to E . For the frequency factor A , Kissinger derived the following semi-empirical expression for n th-order reactions:

$$A = \frac{\phi E \exp(E / RT_p)}{RT_p^2 [n(1 - \alpha_p)^{n-1}]} \approx \frac{\phi E \exp(E / RT_p)}{RT_p^2}$$

Here, α_p is the extent of reaction at the peak exotherm. He argued that $n(1 - \alpha_p)^{n-1} \approx 1$ and is independent of heating rate.

Fig. 6 is the plot of $\ln(\phi / T_p^2)$ against $1/T_p$. The linear regression results are listed in Table 2. It is reasonable that BMI shows the lowest E and A compared with the blends, while E tends to decline with an increase in the PPO content. PPO disperses the BMI monomer in the blends, causing hindrance to the curing process, so resulting in an increase in the activation energy.

Fig. 6 Application of the Kissinger method in kinetics study

Table 2 Kinetic parameters from Kissinger analysis in curing of BMI and its blends

PPO % (wt.)	a	b	R ²	E (kJ/mol)	lnA
0	12143	15.30	0.9931	101.0	24.7
10	16215	22.59	0.9691	134.8	32.2
20	15648	20.98	0.9710	130.1	30.6
30	15137	20.01	0.9877	125.8	29.6
40	15580	20.84	0.9926	129.5	30.5

(a, slope; b, intercept; R², least-square regression coefficient)

Thermogravimetric analysis

Samples of BMI, PPO and their blends were tested in a Perkin-Elmer TGA 7. The diagrams shown in Fig. 7 exhibit the pattern of one-stage degradation for all the samples. This proves the semi-IPN structure of the BMI/PPO blends and indicates the retardance of degradation of the PPO phase when confined by the BMI network.

The relevant parameters in the decomposition of the materials are listed in Table 3. The maximum decomposition temperature (T_{max}) obtained from the first derivative analysis indicates the temperature under which a drastic decomposition and an overall break-down of the material occurs. $T_{1/2}$ is known as the temperature at 50% weight retention, and the final weight retention at the end of material decomposition is the char yield. A comparison of the onset decomposition temperature (T_{onset}) and T_{max} at different PPO contents clearly shows that both T_{onset} and T_{max} decrease with an increase in the PPO content (Fig. 8), but apparent drop is not observed until the PPO content reaches 20%. When the simple rule of mixtures (dotted

lines) is taken for comparison, it is found that the T_{onset} of the blend sample is lower than the temperature estimated from the mixing rule, while T_{max} gives higher values. The drop in T_{onset} for the blended samples may be due to the possible presence of an un-confined PPO phase which causes the early degradation of parts of the sample. Nonetheless, the overall semi-IPN structure contributes to the heat-resistance of the blend, hence raises T_{max} , which is the characteristic parameter for the heat-resistant property of the entire material. In other words, PPO's thermogravimetric resistance is improved by blending with BMI. Moreover, a decrease is observed in both $T_{1/2}$ and the char yield with the increase in the PPO content of the blends. It is expected that the char yield follows the mixing rule (dotted line in Fig. 9) since it is a mixture of the ashes of the BMI and PPO.

Fig. 7: Thermogravimetric analysis of BMI, PPO and BMI/PPO blends

Table 4: TGA results for BMI and its blend systems

PPO % (wt.)	T_{onset} (°C)	T_{max} (°C)	$T_{1/2}$ (°C)	Char yield (%)
0	549.9	556.6	757.8	46.7
5	550.0	562.7	692.9	43.4
10	544.9	556.5	698.8	43.7
15	545.4	559.8	695.8	42.6
20	543.7	561.0	672.3	39.7
25	535.8	551.5	685.8	42.8
30	530.1	549.4	681.7	42.7
40	526.2	553.4	638.0	38.9
50	520.6	543.2	653.9	38.9
100	513.9	531.5	541.3	28.4

Fig. 8: TGA decomposition temperature

Fig.9: Char yield for BMI/ PPO blends

Thermomechanical analysis

While dynamic TGA provides an indication of short-term thermal stability, TMA studies the mechanical changes during heating including the expansion of samples. Fig. 10 is the TMA thermographs for BMI material and its blends with 10-30% PPO. Apparently there is no obvious change in dimensions over the wide temperature range up to 400 °C, and the simple thermal expansion is fairly steady. None of the glass-transitions in both BMI and PPO phases can be observed from the thermographs. The high crosslink density of the network structure in the materials is believed to restrict the mobility of the molecular segments and thus suppresses the dimensional changes in the materials under test. The PPO phase is extensively distributed in the BMI network and its segmental movement is greatly restricted by the network structure. Therefore, the promising thermal mechanical stability is reflected from the TMA results of BMI and its blends with PPO. However, a difference in the change of expansion coefficient in different temperature ranges is noticeable as shown in Table 4. In the high temperature range (300-350 °C), BMI gives smaller expansion coefficient as the result of its high crosslink density of the network. Higher expansion coefficients are observed for the blend samples due to the higher expansion coefficient of embedded PPO ($5.2 \times 10^{-5}/^{\circ}\text{C}$) [10] in the semi-IPN structure.

Fig. 10 Thermomechanical analysis of BMI and BMI/PPO blends

Table 4 Comparison of thermal Expansion coefficient (α) from TMA

α ($10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$)	BMI	10% PPO	20% PPO	30% PPO
50 ~ 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	10.8	18.8	9.3	8.6
300 ~ 350 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	10.1	29.1	19.7	18.3

CONCLUSION

BMI exhibits good miscibility in blending with PPO through solution method. Optical microscopy shows the dispersion of BMI phase with the increase in PPO content. The PPO phase affects the curing behaviour of BMI in the blends, increasing its curing temperature and reducing the reaction heat. On the other hand, BMI's melting behaviour is quite independent upon the presence of PPO. The improvement in PPO's thermostability has been confirmed in the blends through TGA and TMA analyses. The semi-IPN structure is also verified through TGA experiments.

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